

Comparing Habitants' and Visitors' Perceptions of Places via Social Media Reviews

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Abstract. In this paper, we emphasise that people with different personal experiences develop different perceptions of particular places in New Orleans. We distinguish between habitants of and visitors to that city based on users' digital footprints provided by social media data (Yelp). Afterwards, we apply the Long-Short-Term-Memory method to capture people's feelings, either positive or negative, about different places. We further employ term frequency/inverse document frequency to explain the place-specific characteristics that elicit differing feelings among habitants and visitors. Ultimately, we aim to contribute to the literature on place semantics by linking place-specific characteristics to the emotional experiences of different people.

Keywords. Place Perceptions, Feeling Map, Natural Language Processing

1. Introduction

We aim to investigate people's feelings about places and explore whether there are differences in the way that 'habitants' and 'visitors' score and describe places they go to in New Orleans. Specifically, utilising social media data, we aim to answer how to categorise and distinguish habitants and visitors based on their check-in footprints, and capture the emotions and words used to describe place characteristics in their reviews.

2. Data & Methods

2.1. Data Collection & Research Design

We conduct a case study on New Orleans using data from the Yelp dataset. Our sample includes 635,416 reviews from 245,469 users across 6,218

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businesses, spanning March 14, 2005, to January 19, 2022. The workflow of our proposed method is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The workflow of this work.

2.2. Distinguishing between Habitants and Visitors

To distinguish between habitants and visitors of New Orleans, we consider the time difference between users’ first and last reviews and the pattern of their review activity, examining whether their reviews are concentrated within a short period or dispersed over time. First, we identify and exclude inactive users to avoid misclassification. Inactive users typically post a few reviews, often within a single day. Their limited use of Yelp and the lack of data from other cities make it difficult to determine their residence. For the remaining users, we calculate the longest, shortest, and New Orleans-specific time differences between their reviews. We then analyse their review patterns across cities to determine their classification as habitants or visitors in New Orleans.

2.3. Find ‘Divisive’ Places

We draw on Rofè (2004)’s “feeling map” idea, which surveys and maps people’s emotional responses to their environment. Instead of interviews, we use deep learning methods to extract feelings from reviews (e.g. positive, negative, or neutral). We apply the Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) neu-

ral network, which captures contextual semantic information and is effective in text classification (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Long Short-Term Memory Architecture (Source: Own elaboration based on Hochreiter & Schmidhuber(1997)).

2.4. Extract Features of Divisive POIs

To analyse factors influencing feeling differences, we use the term frequency/inverse document frequency (TF-IDF) to extract place features, focusing primarily on the divisive places identified in Section 2.3. TF-IDF highlights terms frequent in a document but rare in others, effectively representing the document (Feick & Robertson, 2015). We preprocess the text by removing stop words, tagging part-of-speech and extracting high-frequency words. Then we only extract nouns, adjectives and adverbs that appeared more than thirty times for calculating the TF-IDF.

3. Results

3.1. Validate the Classification of Habitants and Visitors

To validate the effectiveness of our classification method for habitants and visitors, we compare the frequency of place types visited by the two groups, as habitants and visitors tend to frequent different places (Zhang et al., 2020). Figure 4 shows the frequency distribution of various POI categories for each group. Restaurants, nightlife, and food-related POIs dominate visits for both groups. In New Orleans, restaurants, museums, and retail

shops are mainly tourism-driven (Gladstone, 2012), while eating-related activities are essential to both groups’ daily lives. The “Hotels & Travel” category sees higher visitation frequency from visitors than from habitants. In contrast, habitants visit categories associated with local lifestyles, such as “Beauty & Spas”, “Pets”, and “Real Estate” at higher rates.

Figure 3. Frequency ranking of visits to various POI categories by habitants (left) and visitors (right).

3.2. Find ‘Divisive’ Places

We analyse the predominant emotions for each Business_ID from habitants and visitors, focusing on places with ‘divisive’ reactions —where habitants feel positive and visitors negative, or vice versa. Neutral sentiment places were excluded to highlight places with more pronounced differences. These divisive places were then grouped by POI type, and the top 10 categories visited by both groups were plotted. Restaurants show the most contrast, while emotion for Active Life POIs remained consistent. We then examine the descriptive words used by habitants and visitors for Restaurants and Active Life.

Figure 4. Spatial distribution and frequency ranking of divisive places.

3.3. The Relationship between Feature Lexicons and People’s Sentiment

The results indicate that habitants’ negative reviews of certain restaurants often cite issues such as waiting time, price, taste, noise, and the requirement to drive to the location. They also mentioned food delivery options (e.g. Uber, online, delivery). Conversely, visitors rate these same restaurants positively, emphasising the atmosphere and environment with words like “friendliest”, “relax”, “excellent”, and “unforgettable”. Visitors also highlight elements like “pic”, “views”, “magazine”, “babies”, and “playing”, and find the price and location acceptable. For restaurants where habitants feel positive but visitors feel negative, habitants value price (“inexpensive”), atmosphere (e.g. romantic, chic) and food quality (“seasoned” and “deliciousness”). Visitors, however, cite dissatisfaction with price, taste and cleanliness.

Negative(habitants)	Positive(visitors)	Positive(habitants)	Negative(visitors)
Tasteless	Impression	Seasoned, classics	Tasteless
Drive	Friendliest, relax, excellent	Comfort,romantic,chic	Unimpressive
Noise	Unforgettable	Families	Luggage
Waited, waitlist		Uptown	Renovations
Dollars coupon	Pic, views, magazine,	Deliciousness	Prices
Uber online delivery	Child, babies, playing	Covid	Trash, dush, sewage, cleanliness, garbage
	Pounds, cheapest, specials, offers	Accommodate, celebration	Quantity
	Parking	Views	Sight
	Closest	Memories	Undercooked, unseasoned
	Accessible	Innovative	Address
	Professionalism	Regularly	Facilities
		Prompt	
		Dollars, inexpensive	

Table 1. Differences in emotions elicited by specific features of restaurants.

In the “Active Life” category, sentiments are generally similar, but some differences exist. Habitants express dissatisfaction with location, experience (“boring”), and overcrowding (“people”). Visitors highlight positive aspects like companionship (“friends”), venue aesthetics (“beautiful”, “large”), affordability (“cheap”) and availability. For places where habitants feel happy, they praise service, facilities, cleanliness, lighting, and the presence of children or dogs. Visitors, however, express dissatisfaction with issues like packages, unused facilities, and other unspecified concerns.

Negative(locals)	Positive(nonlocals)	Positive(locals)	Negative(nonlocals)
Boring	Fun	Service	Package
Location	Friends	Instructors	Problem
Experience	Local	Price, free	Unused
Small	Beautiful	Minutes	
People	Neighbourhood	Clean	
	Large	Drinks	
	Free	Dog	
	Experience	Lights	
	Staff	Facility	
	Available	Kids, Location	
	People	Water	
	Water	People	
		Music	

Table 2. Differences in emotions elicited by specific features of Active Life.

4. Conclusion

We presented preliminary semantic analysis using social media review data to discern differences in feelings and perceptions attached to place between habitants and visitors. We focused on ‘divisive’ places where the two groups exhibit differing emotions, explaining the varying levels of attention each group pays to different place features.

References

- Feick, R., & Robertson, C. (2015). Identifying Locally- and Globally-Distinctive Urban Place Descriptors from Heterogeneous User-Generated Content. In F. Harvey & Y. Leung (Eds.), *Advances in Spatial Data Handling and Analysis* (pp. 51–63). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-19950-4_4
- Gladstone, D. L. (2012). Event-based urbanization and the New Orleans tourist regime: A conceptual framework for understanding structural change in US tourist cities. *Journal of Policy Research in Tourism, Leisure and Events*, 4(3), 221–248. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19407963.2012.711086>
- Hochreiter, S., & Schmidhuber, J. (1997). Long Short-Term Memory. *Neural Computation*, 9(8), 1735–1780. <https://doi.org/10.1162/neco.1997.9.8.1735>
- Rofè, Y. (2004). Mapping people's feelings in a neighborhood: Technique, analysis and applications. *Planum: The Journal of Urbanism*, 9(2), 1–26.
- Zhang, F., Zu, J., Hu, M., Zhu, D., Kang, Y., Gao, S., Zhang, Y., & Huang, Z. (2020). Uncovering inconspicuous places using social media check-ins and street view images. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 81, 101478. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2020.101478>